

Telomeres: The EPI-Ending

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Abstract

Telomeres are essential chromosomal structures that protect genome integrity and play a central role in aging and cell proliferation. In plants, the epigenetic landscape of telomeres and their adjacent subtelomeric regions has emerged as a critical component regulating telomere function and genome organization. This review summarizes current knowledge of chromatin modifications at plant telomeres, and the impact of chromatin-associated factors on telomere stability. We also discuss experimental tools for studying telomere epigenetics, and identify key open questions in the field.

Introduction

Telomeres are repetitive DNA elements at the ends of linear chromosomes that safeguard chromosome stability and prevent DNA damage responses. While the basic structural features of telomeres are conserved, plants exhibit unique patterns in their telomere-associated chromatin states. Understanding how epigenetic modifications contribute to telomere maintenance is crucial to see broader aspects of plant genome regulation, ageing, and adaptation. There is an initial concept of chromatin (including the telomeric one) as a relatively static entity that originated from

immobile microscopy images. In these images, satellites appear densely stained, which led to the classical definition of euchromatic and heterochromatic regions. However, rapid advances in sequencing technologies have shifted this view toward a more dynamic model, where individual chromatin states emerge as a consequence of combined epigenetic modifications (further defining chromatin accessibility) and three-dimensional nuclear architecture [1,5,6]. Repetitive elements are thus no longer seen as merely inactive; rather, their activity depends on the balance of active and repressive chromatin marks.

Plastic Ends: Evolutionary Diversification of Telomeric Sequences in Plants

Most plant telomeres consist of a repeated minisatellite sequence, which was initially thought to consist exclusively of the TTTAGGG motif [7]. However, more systematic analyses across the evolutionary tree have revealed considerable variation in telomeric sequence composition within the plant kingdom. Acknowledging that the list is probably not exhaustive, alternative motifs have been identified in selected species of *Asparagales*, including monocots in *Sciloidea* subfamily [8-10] and crop species *Allium cepa* (onion) [11]; *Cestrum elegans* from the family Solanaceae, where the model plant *Nicotiana tabacum* (tobacco) also belongs [12], and in carnivorous plants such as *Genlisea hispidula* [13]. These alternative telomeres either consist of variations or mixtures of other conserved sequence motifs - human (TTAGGG)_n or Tetrahymena (TTGGGG)_n, sometimes intermingled with canonical plant sequence - or contain entirely novel motifs differing in both length and composition. While the first scenario predominates in *Sciloideae* [8-10], our work shows that *Allium* telomeres evolved significantly and contain CTCGGTTATGGG motif [14]. Longer telomeric repeat sequence was also found in *Cestrum elegans*, TTTTTTAGGG [15], whereas shorter repeat lengths remain in *G. hispidula* - TTCAGG and TTTCAGG [13]. These findings, which highlight the plasticity of telomere sequences while maintaining telomere canonical functions, raised new questions about whether the chromatin state changes in the context of alternative telomeres, and whether telomere length or sequence variability plays a role [16].

In fact, this may resemble the situation observed in centromeres, which also display remarkable variations, even within species or individuals, despite the initial idea that centromeres are well-conserved and composed of constitutive heterochromatin [17-19].

Telomeric Chromatin: A Distinct Epigenetic Domain

In the combinatorial model of chromatin, the presence of DNA methylation, histone variants and their post-translational modifications (PTMs) - methylation, acetylation or other marks - defines the structure and activity of each chromatin region [5,6]. While centromeric satellites are typically

marked by centromeric histone H3 (CENH3), telomeres do not possess a specific histone variant of their own, but they are enriched in histone H3.3 instead [20]. H3.3 is typically found at the gene bodies and regulatory elements (5' and 3') and associates with transcription, recombination, and DNA repair [21,22]. Pilot chromatin immunoprecipitation and sequencing (ChIP-seq) experiments in *Arabidopsis thaliana* revealed that telomeres are less heterochromatic than centromeres, based on the distribution of H3.1 and H3K9me2 marks [20,23]. Interestingly, the idea of centromeric chromatin has also undergone an in-depth revision, and the most recent work describes it as a hybrid structure, with a heterochromatic (H3K9me2-labelled and methylated) profile in the pericentromeric regions, and a more open configuration at the sites occupied by CENH3 [24]. This configuration reduces non-CG methylation and H3K9me2, and allows for H3K4me2 incorporation. Therefore, the presence of H3.3 at telomeres might have a similar impact on telomeric chromatin as CENH3 at centromeres - possibly allowing for activation of transcription, recombination and DNA repair to take place. In the case of altered telomere function, this may further stimulate alternative lengthening, leading to undesired telomere elongation or shortening [25-27].

Despite the rapid technological advances of the past decade, the epigenetic map of telomeres remains elusive due to specific methodological issues complicating the analysis of the telomeric chromatin. Telomeres, as repetitive sequences, have been markedly under-represented in the ChIP-seq datasets. Besides, the data analysis requires distinguishing genuine telomeres from telomeric repeats embedded within chromosomes - so-called interstitial telomeric repeats (ITRs). These are frequently found in centromeric, pericentromeric, and subtelomeric regions of many plant species [28-30] and in contrast to perfect telomeric repeats present at the chromosome ends, often intermingled by other sequences or degenerated telomeric motifs. Setting the longer telomere motif in the data analysis pipeline enables the elimination of non-specific reads and increases the reliability of the telomere detection [23]. Similarly, ITRs contribute to the telomere signal also in ChIP-dot blot experiments, in which the representation of telomeric DNA in immunoprecipitated fractions is analyzed by hybridization. Using the dot-blot hybridization under highly stringent conditions to minimize the contribution of ITR-derived signal, a dual character of *Arabidopsis* telomeres, decorated with both heterochromatin and euchromatin-specific epigenetic marks was shown [31,32]. In addition, we evaluated telomeric chromatin in a set of plants with telomeres formed by either canonical or non-canonical repeats and revealed two combinatorial patterns of telomere histone marks. *Arabidopsis*-like telomeres with dominant H3K9me2, and tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*)-like group in which H3K27me3 predominated. To increase the credibility of these results, patterns of telomere histone marks were confirmed in *Arabidopsis* and tobacco using the ChIP with the purified fraction of telomeric chromatin [16]. Moreover, in *N.*

tabacum, no relevant fraction of ITRs was found [29], thus their contribution could be excluded. It seems that the distribution of telomeric histone modifications is rather stochastic, as classification of plants into these groups was related neither to the telomeric repeat sequence, to the length of telomeres, genome size, nor the phylogenetic position of the respective plant, **Figure 1**. Both these patterns of telomeric histone marks decorate telomeres able to accomplish fully their canonical functions; recognition of natural chromosome ends and protection of internal chromosome parts from the replicative shortening.

Continuing the in-depth investigation of numerous ChIP-seq datasets finally led to the conclusion that telomeres in *A. thaliana* are not strongly enriched in either euchromatic (H3K4me2, H3K9ac, and H3K27me3) or heterochromatic (H3K9me2, H3K27me1) marks to levels comparable with typical euchromatic and heterochromatin regions, respectively [33]. A similar scenario also occurs in mammals, where H3K9me3, a hallmark of heterochromatin [34,35], as well as activating PTMs (e.g., H3K27ac and H4K20me1) were found [36]. Vaquero-Sedas and Vega-Palas [33] further stressed the impact of heterochromatic subtelomeres on the structure and function of epigenetically undetermined telomeres. Although the heterochromatic nature of subtelomeres is a widely accepted concept, actively transcribed genes situated in euchromatic environments have been identified in close proximity to certain Arabidopsis telomeres [32]. Therefore, even though some agreement has been reached regarding the structural model of plant telomeric chromatin, the functional interplay between telomeres and adjacent regions is still awaiting final clarification.

Similarly, the methylation of telomeric cytosines remains an unresolved issue. Cytosines in the C-rich strand of the canonical plant telomere repeat, CCCTAAA, are natural targets for methylation as plant *de novo* methyltransferases are able to modify cytosines in all sequence contexts, including those located asymmetrically [37]. In a pilot work reporting *A. thaliana* genome methylation at a single-nucleotide resolution, a certain, relatively low level of methylated telomeric cytosines was reported [38]. Nevertheless, in this study, as well as in subsequent studies based on dot-blot hybridization of the bisulfite-modified DNA [31,32,39,40], ITRs contribution cannot be excluded. Promising solution to this problem is a capability of third-generation sequencing methods enabling “telomere-to-telomere” genome assembly, e.g., PacBio and Oxford Nanopore Technologies, to distinguish methylated bases, including methylcytosine [41,42]. For example, in a recent complete assembly of the maize genome, telomeres of the average length of 26 kb were found at the chromosome ends [41]. These data, together with datasets from other plants, remain to be comprehensively evaluated.

Telomere Team: Role of Telomeric and Non-Telomeric Players

The importance of the chromatin environment for telomere stability can be demonstrated indirectly using plants deficient in histone loading and processing. It was shown, for example, that the inability of H3.3 to be methylated at lysine 36 led to the reduction of lifespan in fly [43] and RNAi-depletion of H3.3 caused telomere dysfunction in mouse embryonic stem cells [35]. Though *A. thaliana* H3.3 and H3.1 deficient lines were not investigated for telomere profiles, their phenotypes are reminiscent of the histone chaperone mutants [3,22,44,45]. Recent work by our group and others, employing plants deficient in different H3 histone chaperones - the CHROMATIN ASSEMBLY FACTOR 1 (CAF-1), the ANTI-SILENCING FUNCTION 1 (ASF1) or HISTONE REGULATOR A (HIRA), confirmed that the balanced composition of H3 plays important role in the telomere stability [2,3,45,46], **Figure 2**. The overall imbalance of H3 histone variants led to a redistribution of the DNA repair-related variant H2A.W.7 and a repurposing of H3.3 through changes in its epigenetic signature [4], **Box 1**. Though the extent of these changes on telomeres is currently unknown in plants, histone chaperones remain key players in the maintenance of telomere chromatin as suggested in other model organisms [3,25,47].

Our recent findings also highlight a regulatory role for linker histone H1 in maintaining epigenetic homeostasis at both telomeres and pericentromeric ITRs [48], by limiting the DNA accessibility to TELOMERE REPEAT BINDING (TRB) proteins, the plant-specific Myb-related factors [49-51]. TRB proteins, among other telomere-specific functions, guide recruitment of POLYCOMB REPRESSIVE COMPLEX 2, involved in H3K27 methylation [51,52]. Consistently, the H1 deficiency leads to the excessive accumulation of H3K27me3 at telomeric sequences [48]. An additional key finding was the identification of TRB's role within the broader context of chromatin-associated complexes - the histone demethylase JUMONJI14 [53], the PEAT complex PWOs-EPCRs-ARIDs-TRBs [54,55] and possibly also ASF1, as we recently found [46]. Since we also learned that TRB proteins associate with the short telomeric repeats (*tel*o-boxes) present in the promoters of many genes [56], they likely recruit other chromatin remodeling complexes to these 5' regulatory regions.

When discussing proteins associated with telomeric chromatin in plants, distinct differences are observed compared to those identified in other organisms, such as mammals and yeast. To date, no plant equivalent of the mammalian Shelterin [57,58] - a six-subunit, telomere-specific protein complex - has been identified. Interestingly, although Arabidopsis possesses proteins structurally similar to the core components of the mammalian Shelterin complex, known as TRF-like proteins, these do not appear to participate in telomere maintenance [59] and require an accessory Myb-

extension domain for binding telomeric dsDNA *in vitro* [60]. Therefore, to date, TRB proteins are the only proteins with confirmed association with plant telomeres, demonstrated by different means [49,61,62]. They interact directly with telomerase and are implicated in telomere maintenance [50]. With respect to the very many functions of the TRB proteins and missing evidence for other plant telomere-specific proteins, it appears that the epigenetic status and chromatin architecture of telomeres, rather than a defined multiprotein complex, may play a central role in protecting linear telomeres from degradation.

Declaration of competing interest

Authors declare that there are neither financial nor personal competing interests.

Data availability

No data was used for this review article.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to edit and correct the writing style. After using these tools, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Box 1. Fine-tuning of epigenetic landscape in *caf-1* deficient plants

Genome stability varies with different H3 chaperone deficiencies. In plants, CAF-1 loss leads to the pleiotropic defect, including sensitivity to genotoxic agents, the emergence of large tandem duplications, and repeat instability [1-3]. Faulty loading of H3.1 variant triggers the adaptive epigenetic changes at the level of post-translational modifications (PTMs) and H2A histone variants, as revealed by high-resolution mass spectrometry [4]. Interesting aspect in the histone variant regulation is the lack of prevalence of homotypic H3 nucleosomes, described for H2 variants [5], which adds to the complexity of the epigenetic re-programming. In *fas1* plants, deficient in the largest subunit of CAF-1, defective H3.1 loading results in reduced H3.1K27 monomethylation, and increased H3.1K27 trimethylation. This is accompanied by lower level of H3.3K36me1, a mark linked to the transcription and DNA repair. Interestingly, genotoxic stress induced by zeocin increases H3.3K27me1 primarily in *fas1*, while further reducing H3.3K36 methylation as the mutant attempts to maintain PTMs balance. The most pronounced effect is observed in the *fas1nap1* plants, which have an additional dysfunction in three NUCLEOSOME ASSEMBLY PROTEINS. In these mutants, many phenotypic defects improve, the H3.1:H3.3 is largely restored and H3.3 PTM pattern closely resembles that of the H3.1 variant [3,4]. Compensation also involves the H2A.W.6 variant, important for chromocenter formation, and the DNA repair-associated H2A.W.7 variant, which becomes redistributed within the nuclear subdomains in *fas1*. Whether a similar scenario occurs at telomeres remains unclear and will be extremely challenging to investigate.

Figure legends:

Figure 1. Epigenetic landscape of plant telomeres is uncoupled from telomere length, telomeric repeat type, and genome size.

Chromatin immunoprecipitation experiments using purified telomeric chromatin fractions confirmed the distinct histone modification patterns at telomeres across different plant species, allowing classification into two subgroups:

The first group, exemplified by *Arabidopsis thaliana*, displays a dominant H3K9me2 signal and includes *Arabidopsis*, *Allium*, *Petunia*, *Narcissus* and two *Solanum* and *Genlisea* species. In some of these plants (upper panel), other three analyzed histone marks (H3K27me3, H3K4me2, H3K4me3) were detected to varying degrees. In others (middle panel), H3K9me2 was found to co-occur with H3K27me3 [16]. In *Arabidopsis*, H3K27me1 was previously also detected on telomeres (not shown; see [32]). The bimodal organization of *Arabidopsis* telomeric chromatin was further confirmed by [33]. The “tobacco-like” group is characterized by a predominance of H3K27me3, as seen in two *Nicotiana* species (with canonical telomeres) and *Cestrum elegans* (with atypical telomeres). Importantly, euchromatic marks H3K4me2/3 were below the detection limit in several species, including *Petunia* and both *Solanum* species. These observations suggest that the distribution of telomeric histone marks is stochastic and not correlated with telomere repeat type, telomere length, genome size, or phylogenetic position.

Figure 2. Role of histone chaperones in the stability of telomeres and centromeres.

Centromeres are defined by the incorporation of the centromere-specific histone H3 variant CENH3, while the surrounding heterochromatic pericentromeric regions are enriched in the H3.1 variant. In contrast, H3.3 is more abundant in telomeric chromatin, which is not typically considered heterochromatic. In plants, CENH3 is deposited by the histone chaperone NASP (NUCLEAR AUTOANTIGENIC SPERM PROTEIN) [63,64], whereas H3.1 and H3.3 are loaded by the chaperones CAF-1, ASF1, and HIRA through both replication-coupled and replication-independent pathways. Mutations in these histone chaperones alter the nuclear pool of H3 variants and their chromosomal distribution, leading to telomere shortening [46,65]. In the case of CAF-1, its disruption additionally causes changes in pericentromeric heterochromatin organization [45].

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The authors propose quality filters that enhance accuracy while retaining the majority of CpG sites. Performance is assessed across genomic features and methylation levels, highlighting improvements with the R10.4 nanopore chemistry. Comparisons with 50 SMRT-sequenced genomes further contextualize the strengths and trade-offs of each method. The study offers practical guidance for standardizing CpG methylation analysis in long-read sequencing.

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This study explores the roles of Arabidopsis histone chaperones ASF1 and HIRA in maintaining telomeres and 45S rDNA loci, regions sensitive to chromatin changes. In both *asf1a/b* and *hira* mutants, telomere lengths are reduced, though telomere localization and H3 levels remain unchanged. Additionally, ASF1 and HIRA regulate 45S rRNA gene silencing and copy number, with ASF1 also supporting global heterochromatin. ASF1 transient interactions with TRB1 and telomerase link ASF1 to telomere maintenance.

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This study investigates the role of histone H1 in maintaining the distribution of H3K27me3 across distinct chromatin domains. In Arabidopsis H1 mutant plants, H3K27me3 is broadly redistributed, with most genes showing the expected loss of this repressive mark. In contrast, telomeres and ITRs become aberrantly enriched in H3K27me3. These findings uncover a dual role for linker histone H1: while it promotes PRC2-mediated H3K27me3 deposition at gene targets, it also prevents excessive accumulation of this mark at telomeric regions by restricting access of TRB proteins.

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- 51**. Kusova A, Steinbachova L, Prerovska T, Drabkova LZ, Palecek J, Khan A, Rigoova G, Gadiou Z, Jourdain C, Stricker T, et al.: **Completing the TRB family: newly characterized members show ancient evolutionary origins and distinct localization, yet similar interactions.** *Plant Mol Biol* 2023, **112**:61-83.

This work shows that TRB4-5 share common TRB motifs and their Myb-like domains bind long arrays of telomeric repeats *in vitro*. The minimal recognition motif for TRB proteins was identified as one *telo*-box (1.2 telomeric units (tAGGGTTT) flanked with non-telomeric DNA). Despite the distinct localization patterns of TRB1-3 and TRB4-5 *in situ*, all members of TRB family mutually interact and also bind to telomerase/PRC2/PEAT complexes

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This study reveals that Arabidopsis TRB4 and TRB5, regulate genes linked to developmental and environmental responses. TRB4 binds active gene promoters marked by H3K4me3 but not H3K27me3, and interacts with PRC2, CURLY LEAF and SWINGER. Despite lacking H3K27me3 enrichment, TRB4/5 are essential for *clf* mutant phenotypes, acting as activators of CLF-controlled genes, including those regulating flowering. TRB4 also shares targets and interacts with TRB1, highlighting a complex network of TRB protein interactions mediating plant development via both PRC2-dependent and independent pathways.

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This study reveals that Arabidopsis TRB proteins not only protect telomeres but also act as dual regulators of gene repression by coordinating PRC2-mediated H3K27me3 deposition and JMJ14-mediated H3K4me3 removal. TRBs physically associate with JMJ14, and both are required to repress target genes by altering histone methylation states. Mutants lacking TRBs or JMJ14 show increased H3K4me3 and gene upregulation. Artificial tethering of TRBs confirms their role in directing epigenetic silencing.

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Papers of particular interest, published within the period of review, have been highlighted as:

* of special interest

** of outstanding interest

Organism	Telomeric sequence	Telomere length (kb)	Genome size (1C, Gb)	Histone marks
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	TTTAGGG	3	0.135	
<i>Genlisea nigrocaulis</i>	TTTAGGG	10-18	0.086	
<i>Narcissus pseudonarcissus</i>	TTAGGG	50-100	23.200	
<i>Allium cepa</i>	CTCGGTTATGG	50-120	16.400	
<i>Petunia hybrida</i>	TTTAGGG	30-40	1.400	
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	TTTAGGG	30-60	0.950	
H3K9me2				

Fig.2

